

Overview of Public Health Examination Results in Tumbang Tahai, Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

As a developing country classified as low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), the disparity in knowledge regarding hypertension and Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) should be a concern for the government. Data from the 2018 Riset Kesehatan Dasar (Riskesdas) showed that the prevalence of hypertension in Central Kalimantan reached 34.47%, compared to 26.7% in the 2013 Riskesdas. The 2018 Riskesdas data also revealed that the prevalence of joint diseases in Central Kalimantan was 7.61%. Various factors such as socioeconomic status, dietary patterns, medication usage, and comorbidities can influence uric acid levels. In essence, achieving good health is a fundamental right for every individual, regardless of their economic and social status. However, in practice, healthcare services have not been able to reach the entire population of the country. To address this issue, Asian Medical Students' Association (AMSA-UPR) conducted a community service in the form of free health examinations in Tumbang Tahai Subdistrict of Bukit Batu District in Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan. The research employed a descriptive method with a quantitative approach based on blood pressure, blood glucose, and uric acid examinations. The results showed that many residents are still experiencing hypertension, but most have normal blood glucose and uric acid levels.

INTRODUCTION

The success of health development in Indonesia cannot be separated from the role of the community in accessing healthcare services. Public health is a crucial aspect that is highly emphasized in Indonesia. Therefore, the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia mandates the establishment of Posyandu (Integrated Health Posts) in every village as an initiative of Community-Based Health Efforts (Kementerian Kesehatan RI, 2013).

In Indonesia, as a developing country categorized as a low-and middle-income country (LMIC), the disparities in knowledge about hypertension and Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) should be a concern for the government. Data from the 2018 Riskesdas (National Basic Health Research) revealed that the prevalence of hypertension in Central Kalimantan reached 34.47%, compared to 26.7% in 2013, indicating a substantial increase within a 5-year period, which can be classified as high (Khodijah, 2023).

Uric acid disease, also known as gout or arthritis gout, is a significant health issue. In 2016, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported that the global incidence of gouty arthritis had reached 20% of the world's population. Data from the 2018 Riskesdas showed that the prevalence of joint diseases (including osteoarthritis, acute and chronic hyperuricemia, and rheumatoid arthritis) in Central Kalimantan was 7.61%. Various factors such as socio-economic status, dietary patterns, medication use, and comorbidities can influence uric acid levels (Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network, 2020). Health factors are closely related to the quality of human resources, and the high or low quality of human resources is determined by health status, education, and income level. Therefore, a relatively good health status is essential for individuals to support all aspects of their life activities (Plianbangchang, 2018).

Hypertension can lead to permanent disability, sudden death, and fatal consequences. Therefore, efforts to prevent and manage hypertension need to be carried out by increasing public awareness and adopting healthier lifestyles. Gout (arthritis gout) is a joint disease caused by high levels of uric acid in the blood. Excessive uric acid levels beyond the normal range can lead to the accumulation of uric acid in the joints and other organs, ultimately resulting in pain, discomfort, and inflammation in the joints (Kementerian Kesehatan, 2019).

In essence, achieving good health is a fundamental right for every individual, regardless of their economic and social status. However, in practice, healthcare services have not yet reached the entire population, especially for the less privileged, and improvements are needed to ensure their satisfaction. Enhancing health status inevitably requires substantial financial resources. Therefore, AMSA-UPR (Asian Medical Students' Association Universitas Palangka Raya) conducts community service in the form of free health examinations in the village of Tumbang Tahai, Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hypertension

Hypertension, also known as high or raised blood pressure, is a condition in which the blood vessels have persistently raised pressure. Blood is carried from the heart to all parts of the body in the vessels. Each time the heart beats, it pumps blood into the vessels. Blood pressure is created by the force of blood pushing against the walls of blood vessels (arteries) as it is pumped by the heart. The higher the pressure, the harder the heart has to pump.

Hypertension is a serious medical condition and can increase the risk of heart, brain, kidney and other diseases. It is a major cause of premature death worldwide, with upwards of 1 in 4 men and 1 in 5 women – over a billion people – having the condition. The burden of hypertension is felt disproportionately in low- and middle-income countries, where two thirds of cases are found, largely due to increased risk factors in those populations in recent decades. The Eighth Joint National Committee (JNC 8) released classification for Hypertension in adults as shown in table below (World Health Organization, 2023).

Table 1. Classification of Hypertension

	Systolic BP (mmHg)	and/or	Diastolic BP (mmHG)
Normal	≤129		≤84
Prehypertension	130-139		85-89
Stage 1 Hypertension	140-159		90-99
Stage 2 Hypertension	≥160		≥100

Diabetes Mellitus

Diabetes is a group of metabolic diseases characterized by hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. The chronic hyperglycemia of diabetes is associated with long-term damage, dysfunction, and failure of differentorgans, especially the eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart, and blood vessels (American Diabetes Association, 2011).

Several pathogenic processes are involved in the development of diabetes. These range from autoimmune destruction of the β -cells of the pancreas with consequent insulin deficiency to abnormalities that result in resistance to insulin action. The basis of the abnormalities in carbohydrate, fat, and protein metabolism in diabetes is deficient action of insulin on target tissues. Deficient insulin action results from inadequate insulin secretion and/or diminished tissue responses to insulin at one or more points in the complex pathways of hormone action. Impairment of insulin secretion and defects in insulin action frequently coexist in the same patient, and it is often unclear which abnormality, if either alone, is the primary cause of the

hyperglycemia. The American Diabetes Association (ADA) released classification for Diabetes as shown in table below (Diabetes Care, 2011).

Table 2. Classification of Diabetes Mellitus

	After Eating	Fasting Plasma Glucose	Hemoglobin A1c	2 Hour Oral Glucose Tolerance Test
Normal	<200	70-99mg/dL	<5.7%	<140mg/dL
Prediabetes	-	100-125 mg/dL	5.7%-6.4%	140-199mg/dL
Diabetes	≥200	>125mg/dL	>6.4%	>199mg/dL

Hyperurecemia

Hyperuricemia is an established risk factor for gout and end-stage kidney disease. Furthermore, various studies have suggested the association of hyperuricemia with all-cause and cardiovascular mortality. However, the definition of hyperuricemia varies in each study; therefore, the threshold value of serum uric acid for increased risk of mortality, which is essential for the initiation of treatment, has not been determined.

When examining the association between uric acid levels and prognosis, several points must be considered. First, hyperuricemia is often accompanied by other risk factors such as hypertension, obesity, diabetes, dyslipidemia, and renal insufficiency. This makes it difficult to determine whether hyperuricemia is an independent risk factor or a mere bystander with the other risk factors. Second, sex differences in the distribution of serum uric acid levels exist, and this may modify the association between serum uric acid levels and mortality. Kementrian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia (Kemenkes RI) released classification Uric acid levels as shown in table below (Konta T., *et al.* 2020).

Table 3. Classification of Hyperurecemia

	Male Uric acid level	Female uric level
Normal	3,4-7 mg/dL	2,4-6mg/dL
Above normal	>7 mg/dL	>6 mg/dL
Below normal	<3,4 mg/dL	<2,4 mg/dL

METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this study is descriptive research with a quantitative approach based on the examination results of blood pressure, blood sugar, and uric acid levels. The research subjects were the community of Tumbang Tahai village who came for health examinations at the health examination post. The team of personnel conducting the examinations consisted

of members of AMSA-UPR under the auspices of the Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Palangka Raya. Although three types of examinations were conducted, not all residents were willing to undergo a comprehensive examination as they were still unfamiliar with these types of examinations. Data collection was carried out as part of the free health examination.

The group was divided into registration, blood pressure examination, blood sugar and uric acid level examination, and data recording of the examination results. Blood pressure measurement is done using an aneroid sphygmomanometer, while blood sugar and uric acid levels are measured using Point of Care Testing (POCT). The health examination activities utilize lancets, alcohol swabs, cotton, ballpoint pens, GCU (Glucose, Cholesterol, Uric acid) test strips, and result sheets. Capillary blood from the respondents is used as the sample.

Registered individuals will receive anamnesis papers and be given a check card to be filled out by the personnel. They will then take this card home to record all the test results obtained. Data recording of the test results is performed at the final station. During the review, feedback was given by the personnel. If the examination results were normal, the team provided recommendations to maintain good health. However, if the results were abnormal, education would be provided, and further examination at the nearest health center or hospital would be recommended.

RESULTS

A total of 52 participants took part in the health examination, comprising 13 males (25%) and 39 females (75%). The age distribution of the participants was as follows: 1 person (1.92%) in the age range of 17-25 years, 6 people (11.54%) in the age range of 26-35 years, 14 people (26.92%) in the age range of 36-45 years, 16 people (30.77%) in the age range of 46-55 years, 10 people (19.23%) in the age range of 56-65 years, and 5 people (9.62%) aged above 65 years. The age range and gender distribution is shown in figure below.

Figure 1. Gender distribution

Figure 2. Age group distribution

The blood pressure examination was conducted on 52 participants, including 13 males and 39 females. Among the male participants, 2 individuals (5.13%) had optimal blood pressure, 5 individuals (38.46%) had normal blood pressure, and 1 individual (7.69%) had high-normal blood pressure. The remaining 38.46% of male participants exhibited varying degrees of hypertension, ranging from stage 1 to stage 3. Detailed descriptions of the male participants' blood pressure status can be observed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Male participants' blood pressure

Among the female participants, 2 individuals (5.13%) had optimal blood pressure, 10 individuals (25.64%) had normal blood pressure, and 7 individuals (17.95%) had high-normal blood pressure. The majority, 51.28%, of female participants showed varying degrees of hypertension, ranging from stage 1 to stage 3. Detailed descriptions of the female participants' blood pressure status can be observed in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Female participants' blood pressure

A total of 52 participants, including 13 males and 39 females, underwent blood sugar examination, all participants were instructed to eat before coming. For the male participants, all individuals had normal blood sugar levels, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Male participants' blood sugar levels

Among the female participants, 35 individuals (89.74%) had normal blood sugar levels, while 4 individuals (10.26%) had above-normal blood sugar levels, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Female participants' blood sugar levels

The uric acid examination was conducted on 52 participants, including 13 males and 39 females. Among the male participants, 53.85% had normal uric acid levels, 30.77% had above-normal uric acid levels, and 15.38% had below-normal uric acid levels, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Male participants' Uric acid level

Among the female participants, 76.92% had normal uric acid levels, while 23.08% had above-normal uric acid levels, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Female participants' Uric acid level

DISCUSSION

The results of the health examination conducted on 52 participants provide valuable insights into the health status of the community. The study included individuals from various age groups, representing a diverse sample. The findings shed light on the prevalence of hypertension, blood sugar levels, and uric acid levels among both male and female participants.

Regarding blood pressure, a significant proportion of male and female participants exhibited normal or high-normal readings. However, a notable percentage of individuals were found to have varying degrees of hypertension.

These results highlight the importance of continuous efforts to raise awareness about blood pressure management and preventive measures against hypertension.

In terms of blood sugar levels, it is noteworthy that all male participants had normal readings, while a small percentage of female participants showed above-normal levels. This indicates a need for continued monitoring and health education to promote healthy lifestyle practices, especially among females, to prevent the development of abnormal blood sugar levels and potential risks associated with it.

For uric acid levels, a considerable number of both male and female participants had normal readings. However, a notable percentage of individuals, especially among males, exhibited above-normal uric acid levels. This finding emphasizes the importance of addressing dietary habits and lifestyle factors that may contribute to elevated uric acid levels and potential health implications.

Overall, the health examination conducted during the Event of The Year (EOTY) serves as a crucial initiative in promoting health awareness and early disease detection within the community. The results offer valuable insights for further health interventions and highlight the necessity of collaborating with healthcare professionals to provide immediate medical attention and necessary interventions for individuals with abnormal examination results. The success of such initiatives lies in continued efforts to promote regular health check-ups and foster a culture of proactive health management among the population.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the blood pressure, blood sugar, and uric acid examinations for the participants of the EOTY are as follows:

Blood Pressure

Out of 52 participants, for male participants, 48.72% had optimal, normal, or high-normal blood pressure, while the remaining 51.28% had varying degrees of hypertension, ranging from stage 1 to isolated systolic hypertension.

Blood Sugar

For the 52 participants, all male participants had normal blood sugar levels (100%), while among the female participants, 89.74% had normal blood sugar levels, and 10.26% had above-normal blood sugar levels.

Uric Acid

Out of the 52 participants, for male participants, 53.85% had normal uric acid levels, 30.77% had above-normal uric acid levels, and 15.38% had below-

normal uric acid levels. Among the female participants, 76.92% had normal uric acid levels, and 23.08% had above-normal uric acid levels.

Through this activity, it is hoped that the community's awareness will grow regarding the importance of regular health check-ups for early disease detection. For future activities, it is recommended to collaborate with other parties, such as having doctors present, so that medication and immediate treatment can be provided if abnormal results are detected.

By conducting such health screenings and raising awareness, it is expected that individuals will take proactive steps towards their health and take necessary actions based on the examination results, leading to better management and prevention of health issues.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so further research is still needed on this topic "Overview of Public Health Examination Results in Tumbang Tahai, Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia."

REFERENCES

Kementerian Kesehatan RI. (2013). Buku Panduan Kader Posyandu Menuju

Keluarga Sadar Gizi: Cetakan Kedua. Jakarta: Kementerian Kesehatan RI.

Khodijah, U. (2023). Pemeriksaan Kesehatan (Hipertensi, Kolesterol Tinggi,

Asam Urat, Gula Darah) di Lingkungan Pendidikan Al-Aitaam

Kabupaten Bandung. Bandung

Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network (2020). Global Burden of

Disease Study 2019 Results.

Plianbangchang, S. (2018). To be in good health. *Journal of Health Research*.

32(3); 182-184.

Kementerian Kesehatan. (2019). *Laporan Nasional Riset Kesehatan Dasar 2018*

Lembaga Penelitian dan Pengembangan Kesehatan. Jakarta

World Health Organization. (2023)

Diabetes care. (2011). 34 Suppl 1(Suppl 1), S62–S69.

<https://doi.org/10.2337/dc11-S062>

Konta, T., Ichikawa, K., Kawasaki, R. et al.(2020) Association between serum

uric acid levels and mortality: a nationwide community-based cohort

study. *Sci Rep* 10, 6066. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-63134-0>